

MODERNIZING OF LAND RECORD IN KARNATAKA: A CASE STUDY ON BHOOMI PROJECT

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Abstract

The Bhoomi project is a landmark and innovative e-Governance project by the Karnataka Government, aimed at digitalization and management of land records. This study analyses the existing issues with the development, implementation of the Bhoomi project in the transformative role of the Revenue Department in segregating land record services in an effective manner. Land record management faced many challenges such as manual record-keeping, management in good condition, inaccuracies, delays, and susceptibility to corruption. This project addresses many issues by providing services in digital format for citizens to access land records online, request Record of Rights, Tenancy, and Crops (RTC) documents, Mutation Records (MR) apply for property mutations, and check status online.

The integration of digital verification by the Geographic Information System (GIS) tools and an online grievance redressal system further strengthens the accuracy, transparency, accountability in land record officers and citizen-friendliness. The Bhoomi significantly reduced the land disputes and has improved trust in the government's land administration practices. This study demonstrates the role of this project as a model for e-governance and highlights the potential for other states in India to replicate its success to achieve greater efficiency, accountability, and public satisfaction in land governance.

Keywords: *Karnataka, Bhoomi project, e-governance, land records, digitization, transparency, corruption, land administration*

Introduction

Land is a stagnant, base and high valued asset for economic development, social and also emotional stability and environmental sustainability. In India, land records have

historically been plagued by inaccuracies, corruption and inefficiencies, leading to disputes, litigation, and hindered development. Government of Karnataka recognised these challenges and launched the Bhoomi project in the early 2000s to digitize land records and streamline land administration processes. The Bhoomi project is the most successful e-governance initiative in India since the beginning of e-Governance emerged, serving as a model for other states and countries.

This paper aims to evaluate the working of Karnataka Bhoomi project, focusing on its objectives, issues in implementation and impact on land record management. The study also identifies the challenges and provides recommendations for its improvement and replication.

Objectives of the Bhoomi Project

The primary objectives of the Bhoomi project are:

1. Digitization of complete Land Records: To convert manual land records into digital format, ensuring accuracy, accessibility, ease of access in safety and transparency.
2. Reduction of Corruption: To minimize corruption by dependency on bureaucrats, eliminating intermediaries to get land documents like RTC, MR, Mutation and sketch and providing direct access to land records.
3. Efficiency in Land Record management and Updating: To streamline the land administration processes in transforming land ownership without hurdles and corruption. Also aimed to reduce the time and cost associated with land transactions.
4. Minimization of Land Disputes in erratic human intervention: This project reduces disputes related to land ownership by maintaining accurate and up-to-date land records with human writing erratic and mismanagement.
5. Self-sufficient and Empowerment of Citizens: Bhoomi project empowers land owners and citizens by providing them with easy access to their land records and enabling them to verify the authenticity of documents.

Implementation of the Bhoomi Project;

The Karnataka Bhoomi project was extended in different phases, with association of many stakeholders, including the Revenue Department, Karnataka Government, the National Informatics Centre initiated by Government of India, and private technology partners like Comat Technologies, etc. The important steps in the implementation process were:

1. Data Collection, Verification and Computerization of Land Document: The first and important phase involved the collection of manual land records from village administrative offices (VAO) and their digitization. This process is vital and base for the entire process and it

includes the entry of data related to property ownership, land uses, and land transactions into a centralized database.

2. Application Software Development: A customized application software was developed to manage the digitized land records. The software made land related documents oriented for the entry into computers, updating, and retrieval of land records.

3. Capacity Building Training for employees: Training programs were conducted for user-like data entry staff, approving authority in various levels of government officials, like VAOs, and other partners to familiarize them with the new system and ensure its effective implementation.

4. Infrastructure Establishment: Bhoomi centers like Nadakacheri, Spandana Centre, Padasale and monitoring agency Bhoomi Centre. Were offices established across the state to provide citizens with access to digitized land records. These centers were connected to e-Governance infrastructures with computers, printers, and internet connectivity.

5. Backend Support System for Integration: The Land Records management system was integrated with many public authorities, such as the revenue department (Mother Department) and the registration department with Kaveri Portal, Panchayat Raj Department with Panchatantra to ensure seamless data flow and coordination.

Impact of the Bhoomi Project

The Bhoomi project has an important impact on the land record management system in Karnataka. The key outcomes of the project are:

Transparency in Land Records: The digitization of land records under the Bhoomi has made them easily accessible to citizens at fingertips. It is reducing the need for intermediaries and enhancing transparency. Citizens can now obtain their land records like RTC, MR, EC, Khata Extract, Survey Documents and Akarbund online at www.https://landrecords.karnataka.gov.in/ or from Bhoomi centers, reducing the time and effort required. Bhoomi Project Service Users data in 2024; Mutation Services – 40%, RTC Download – 25%, Land Record Correction – 20% Survey Requests – 10%, Others – 5%.

- Reduction in Corruption in Obtaining Land Documents: The Bhoomi project eliminating intermediaries and providing direct access to land records, the Bhoomi project has significantly reduced opportunities for corruption from land owners at every time of documents required. Land owners have been receiving land records or updating without bribe and delay.
- Efficiency in Land Record Management: The Bhoomi project has streamlined land records and documents administration processes, reducing the time and cost associated

with land transactions. The online access allows for quick verification and updating of land records, reducing delays and without errors.

- **Minimization of Land Disputes in Ownership and Wrong entry:** The accuracy and up-to-date nature of digitized land records have minimized disputes related to land ownership. An individual can easily verify the authenticity of land records online, reducing the likelihood of litigation.
- **Citizens Centric and User Friendly:** The Bhoomi project has empowered land owners and individuals by providing them with easy access to their land records, documents and enabling them to verify the authenticity of documents. This has increased their confidence in the land management system and reduced their dependence on the middleman's system.

Existing Challenges to Bhoomi Project and Its Progress;

The Karnataka Bhoomi project is one of the successful e-Governance applications towards good governance in India. Despite its success, the Bhoomi has faced several challenges, including:

Digital Literacy: Large portion of the individuals, particularly in rural areas land owners, lacks in digital literacy. Significantly, literate groups of people are not aware and difficult for them to access and use the Bhoomi system. This has limited the project's reach and effectiveness.

Digital Infrastructure: Inadequate digital infrastructure in many land owners and beneficiaries. Many people don't have computers, laptops and good quality internet connectivity and lack of electricity in rural areas. Bhoomi Mobile application is good to use, like Dishank application. This has affected the accessibility and reliability of the system.

Traditional Stakeholders Resistance: The Bhoomi project has suffered from orthodox and traditional stakeholders. VAOs and intermediaries, who have lost their influence and income due to the digitization of land records. This has led to attempts to sabotage the system and misleading these people.

Timely Updating Issue: Ensuring the accuracy and timely updation of land records remains a challenge in bureaucratic mindset. Large number of errors and data entry pending in revenue courts like, Tahasildar Court, Assistant Commissioner Court and Deputy Commissioner Court. This is because delays in updating records can lead to disputes and reduce the effectiveness of the system.

Financial Constraints in extension in an effective manner: The upgradation and maintenance is the vital role in every successful programme. The Bhoomi project requires

significant financial resources from the Government. Financial Scarcity and resources have affected the scalability and sustainability of the project.

Bhoomi Project: Advantages and Disadvantages

The following succinct chart lists the benefits and drawbacks of the Bhoomi Project, Karnataka's premier e-Government land record digitization project:

Aspect	Advantages	Disadvantages
Transparency	Minimizes manual interference in land records, thereby reducing corruption.	Despite digitization, some bureaucrats manage to alter data.
Accessibility	Farmers and citizens can easily access land records online and through kiosks.	issues arise for rural consumers who lack internet access and digital knowledge.
Efficiency	Faster delivery of land records and services like RTC (Record of Rights).	Initial delays and server downtime affect service delivery in some areas.
Revenue Management	Enhances government revenue collection by using precise and up-to-date land data.	Inaccurate taxation or disputes may result from data entry errors.
Legal Support	Helpful in using validated historical evidence to settle land disputes	In local legal contexts, the legality of digital records is occasionally questioned.
Integration	Integrates with other schemes (e.g., crop insurance, bank loans).	Lack of real-time updates when land ownership changes on the ground.
Monitoring	Helpful in settling land disputes using historical data that has been confirmed.	Sometimes local employees oppose change because they worry about losing control.
Farmer Empowerment	In local legal situations, digital records' legality is occasionally questioned.	Due of ignorance, farmers still frequently rely on local accountants.
Cost Saving	Lowers long-term costs by cutting down on intermediaries and bureaucracy.	The initial outlay for training and infrastructure was substantial.
Data Security	A secure central database lowers the possibility of records being lost or damaged.	If not updated or checked on a regular basis, it is susceptible to cyber threats.

Recommendations for Improve mentation of Bhoomi Project under user friendly.

The study addresses the challenges in effectively implementation of Bhoomi project and further user friendly, in the following recommendations are proposed:

Digital Literacy Programs in Curriculum: The government should conduct digital literacy programs through the school and college curriculum. This is an effective mode of

knowledge transformation on digital awareness to rural areas, on how to access and use the Bhoomi system. This will increase the project's reach and effectiveness across the people in two to three generations of the students.

User Friendly Infrastructure Development: The government should take necessary steps to invest in improving infrastructure, such as good quality internet connectivity and electricity, to ensure the reliable operation of the Bhoomi system in all areas. Mainly user-friendly mobile application on Bhoomi Project oriented service access. Common man usually using mobile effective manners, it is also helpful to popularization in users' aspects.

Stakeholder Engagement in Confidence on Digital format: The government should take necessary training and encouragement programmes towards traditional stakeholders, such as VAOs. Senior officers should address their concerns and involve them in the implementation of the Bhoomi project. This will reduce resistance and ensure their cooperation in enhancing the user of Bhoomi project with confidence.

Dispute Settlements on Property Rights under Bhoomi Project: The Karnataka government should implement measures to ensure the accuracy and timely settlement of disputes and updating of land records. Fastrack settlement authorities should be increased under revenue administration. A taskforce should be established and includes regular audits on land record transformation to keep public faith. Bhoomi Project officers should get training for data entry operators, and the use of advanced technologies, such as blockchain, for data verification.

Autonomous administrative Setup and Financial Support: The government should establish an autonomous corporation or council in the leadership of a senior civil service officer. This authority independently controls the land record management. The state government should allocate sufficient financial resources for the maintenance of the Bhoomi project. This includes funding for quality infrastructure development, training programs for staff and officials, and system upgrades.

Conclusion;

The Bhoomi land record project is a pioneering e-governance initiative that has significantly improved land record management in the state of Karnataka and also models for other states. By computerised digital documents or records, the project has effectively enhanced transparency in land ownership, reduced corruption in record perusing, and streamlined land records administration procedure. However, challenges such as digital literacy, infrastructure limitations, and resistance from traditional stakeholders remain. Addressing these challenges through digital literacy programs, infrastructure development,

stakeholder engagement, data quality assurance, and financial support will further improve the effectiveness of the Bhoomi project and enable its replication in other regions.

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